

RESEARCH ON PIPA SCORE ACROSS NATIONAL BOUNDARIES: "YUHEXUAN PIPA SCORE" AND "NANGONG PIPA SCORE" FROM JAPAN

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Abstract

The "Yuhexian Pipa Score" compiled by Wang Lu, a descendant of the Northern School Pipa, in 1900 is a representative work of the Northern School Pipa. Some of the scores were first published in the "Music Magazine" of Peking University (1919-1921). Due to Mr. Wang's unresolved hand condition and subsequent illness, it was not possible to publish all the scores, and some of them were scattered among the public. After several generations of efforts to excavate and organize, in 1991, the People's Music Publishing House published the selected songs of "Yuhexian Pipa Score" in the form of a simplified sheet music. Fujiwara Sadatoshi (807-867 AD), a Japanese envoy to the Tang Dynasty, studied the pipa under Chang'an Liu Erlang for four years (834-838 AD) with two hundred taels of gold and sand, and married Liu Erlang's daughter (skilled in playing the piano and zither); Before leaving, Liu Erlang presented dozens of volumes of music and two pipas, named "Xuan Xiang" and "Qing Shan"; In Yangzhou, Zhenmin once again studied the pipa with 85 year old pipa master Lian Chengwu (Shilang studied for 23 days (838.9.7-9.29 AD), and was gifted a volume of "Various Tunes of Pipa" by him. Zhenmin copied it and added his own postscript, which has been preserved to this day. This is the "Kaicheng Pipa Score" stored by the Imperial Household Agency's Shuling Department in Japan. Zhenmin returned to Japan in 839 and became one of the ancestors of Japanese pipa music. Prince Zhenbao (870-924), son of Emperor Seiwa of Japan (reigned 859-876 AD), was a disciple of Fujiwara Sadatoshi. The "Nangong Pipa Score" compiled by Prince Zhenbao in 921 should be derived from the true biography of Zhenmin. As Zhenmin was a student of Lian Shilang in Yangzhou and Liu Erlang in Chang'an, the source of the information for the "Nangong Pipa Manual" should have come from the score gifted by Liu Erlang in Chang'an. This article analyzes the historical and cultural values of the two from a comparative perspective.

Keywords: Pipa score, Japanese pipa culture, Yu Hexuan pipa score, cross-cultural communication

1、The Northern School Pipa Score "Yu Hexuan Pipa Score".

Wang Lu (1877-1921), also known as Xin Kui, was a Guqin artist from Zhucheng, Shandong Province. A pipa player, his precious work, "Yuhexuan Pipa Spectrum," is a representative of the Northern School of pipa. Pao's representative works. Mr. Wang Lu studied music at Peking University from 1919 to 1921.

When Xi was teaching, he combined the textual part of the "Jade Crane Pipa Score" with the part of the "Pipa Score".

The score of the song was published in the Music Magazine of Peking University. Due to the novice was not cured and could not publish all the music scores. Unfortunately, he died of illness.

He died in 1921. He has written many works, but due to the lack of successors, all of them have not been printed. Xie Yichen, a disciple of Wang Lu's pipa, has transcribed parts of Wang Xinkui's music. The music was passed on to his nephew Xie Yupeng, but unfortunately Xie Yichen also died in 1951. Year passed away. The Collection of Shandong Folk Music published by the Music Publishing House in 1960

In the publication, four pipa pieces performed by Xie Yupeng were included. Xie Yu in 1975 Mr. Peng has passed away. Li Rongsheng began to study the "Jade Crane Pipa Score" in 1960, Excavate and sort out the lost music scores. I have visited Xie Yupeng twice in Qingdao Mr. and listened to his performance of the Northern Pipa music, which benefited him a lot.

In 1962, Wang Lu's disciple of Guqin, Mr. Li Huaxuan (from Jinan), Some of the music scores published by Wang Lu in the Music Magazine of Peking University

The Gongche Pipa score was translated into the five-line staff and simplified notation, and handed over to Li Rongsheng for assistance in performance and arrangement and publish the music score. In 1965, Li Huaxuan died of illness.

The 1985 National Higher Music Institute Pipa

At the teaching exchange meeting, Li Rongsheng will personally compile the "Jade Crane Pipa"

The Pipa Score was printed in a book and the paper "The Transmission of the Yuhexuan Pipa Score" was published Spectrum and Arrangement (published in the third issue of New Music of Yuefu in 1987), It was well received by the experts and professors present at the meeting.

In 1986, Wu Ben wrote an article to give a summary of the achievements made in the compilation of mimeograph spectra

High praise: "Thank you, Li Huaxuan, Xie Yupeng, and Li Rongsheng. They have done a very meaningful job for our national music heritage

The excavation and sorting of the site has filled a gap the article also made a Comprehensive analysis and research. After more than 30 years, written by Li Rongsheng, Li Huaxuan, Xie Yupeng the "Jade Crane Pipa Score" compiled by Li Rongsheng and his two colleagues was published in 1991 People's Music Publishing House publishes in the form of simplified notation.

The book has a preface by Wang Lu "Volume" the theoretical part of the text. The "Zhongju" is the pre-recorded "Huashi" of the predecessors Six ancient songs from the "Spectrum". The "next volume" includes 10 pieces of music from Wang Xinkui's biography, of which 7 are representative pieces of the Northern School and 3 are from the Southern School of pipa Xiaoqu, a total of 16 pieces of music were published (due to the "continuation" 8 by Wang Lu

The first piece of music was lost and never returned, so the book is titled "Jade Crane Pipa Selection".

This has brought the art of the Northern Pipa to the world again.

In 1994, the National Key Project published "Chinese Folk Instrumental Music the Collection of Music, which includes seven representative pieces of the Northern School of Pipa (composed by Li Rong sound recording of performance).

Li Rongsheng's paper was published in the third issue of Chinese Musicology in 1994 The Legacy of the Northern School of Pipa demonstrates the musical significance of the Yuhexuan Pipa Score Style and artistic contribution of music (thesis won the social science category of the Shandong Provincial Education Commission

The Research Paper Award.

In 1996, Qingdao People's Broadcasting Station recorded a special music program "Northern Pipa Music, the Descendants in Shandong", ten Northern Pipa

songs performed by Li Rongsheng the performance of Pipa music by the Northern School has filled the void in the sound of Pipa performance. This section the first "Shandong Liu Xie Literary and Artistic Criticism Award" was awarded to the company. Same name paper Included in the "1997 Sixth Shanghai International Radio Music Festival Academic Selected Research Papers." In 2006, the feature program "Pipa Music of the Northern School", The Disciple in Shandong, which was recorded by Shandong Audio-Visual Publishing House, attached to the Chinese and Foreign Famous Instrumental Music published by China International Broadcasting Publishing House

In the song.

In June 1997, Shanghai Music Publishing House published the book "Chinese Pipa" Pai Ming Qu Hui Cui includes the famous pipa music of the Northern School, which was composed by Wang Xinkui

Five songs.

In July 2012, Li Rongsheng was invited as a guest to attend the "Liaoyuan the first International Pipa Culture and Art Festival", and make a talk on the Northern School of Pipa

The special lecture was well received by the participants.

In 2014, Li Rongsheng's "On the Northern School of Pipa" was published in the "Min Dialogue of Space-time of Ethnic Music Culture.

(Yu Hexuan's Pipa score)

2、Sino Japanese musical instrument exchange in Tang Dynasty

During the Sui and Tang Dynasties, the country was unified, the economy was prosperous, the culture was developed, and the transportation was convenient. The ruling class adopted an enlightened national policy and the policy of opening to the outside world, and maintained friendly exchanges with many countries in Asia, Africa and Europe, which also led to the prosperity of national relations and foreign relations. At that time, the number of countries that traded with China increased from more than a dozen to more than 70, including Silla, Japan, India, Afghanistan, Persia, Dashi, Eastern Rome and other countries. It has made contributions to the development of world civilization through diplomatic envoys, sending overseas students, trade exchanges, cultural and technological exchanges, etc.

The music exchange between China and Japan dates back to the Qin and Han Dynasties in China (221

B.C. -220 B.C.), which is equivalent to Japan's mori-bund era. The Tang Dynasty is the most glorious chapter in the history of Sino Japanese music exchange. Since the Zhenguan period of the Tang Dynasty, Sino Japanese trade has been frequent. The mission to Tang Dynasty is to learn the ritual and music system and the art of music, song and dance in the Tang Dynasty, and carry out relevant exchange activities through the head musician and the music student; Following the ritual and music system of the Tang Dynasty, the Japanese court also set up institutions in charge of music, such as yaleyiao and neijiaofang. At the same time, a large number of musical instruments, music scores and music books of the Tang Dynasty were introduced. It can be said that the exchange of music culture between China and Japan has greatly enriched and prospered Japanese music. This paper studies the variety, application and development of musical instruments introduced to Japan during the Tang Dynasty.

Japan through China; 3. Objects made or created by Japan in the Nara era to imitate Chinese cultural relics.

Among them, there are 15 middle and 59 pieces of musical instruments preserved in zhengcangyuan. In 1920, the Japanese musicians Masahiro shangzhenxing, Tadaoki and Tanabe Shangxiong conducted the first survey on the Tang Dynasty musical instruments stored in the zhengcangyuan. Lin Qiansan, Masao kisanabe, takioichi and chiyoutai conducted two surveys on the Tang Dynasty musical instruments stored in the zhengcangyuan in 1948 and 1952, respectively. The musical instruments are as follows (including incomplete musical instruments):

Jinyinping Wenqin 1; Se (24 strings) 1, incomplete; Zheng (13 strings) 4, incomplete; Harp 2, incomplete; Pipa 5; Rosewood five stringed Pipa 1; Ruan xian2; Chi BA 8; Gan Zhu Xiao 1; Horizontal flute 4; Sheng 3; Yu 3; Waist drum 22, incomplete; Thin waist drum 1, incomplete; Fangxiang 1, incomplete.

It is difficult to consider the actual use of the musical instruments stored in the Dongda temple, but most of them are actually my musical instruments stored in the Xida temple. Xida temple is a temple built in the west of Nara, which is opposite to the Dongda temple. The records of tangchuan musical instruments in the Xida Temple assets account are as follows:

Datang musical instruments:

1 pipa, 1 konghou, 1 Fangxiang, 1 Banzhu Hesheng, 1 Banzhu Yu, 2 Chenli, 1 Xiao, 1 Banzhu Chiba, 1 Banzhu horizontal flute, 1 cymbal, 1 Jiegu, 1 waist drum, 1 jilou (drum), 1 inverted drum, 1 xiegu, 1 xiegu, 3 ancient music drums, 1 Dagu, 1 Baizi Lian, and 1 Tang lacquer Qin.

Tang musical instrument:

Six pipas, six red sandalwood dials, six Fangxiang bases, six Sheng pipes, six horizontal flutes, eight Chi pipes, six Da Hu Li pipes, six Xiao Hu Li pipes, six cymbals, six hundred sons, six hundred sons, six waist drums, six Jie drums, six jilou drums, six Ge drums, six Da Gu drums, and one ancient music drum.

In addition, there are also two Jiyue musical instruments, zhengpan, 60 Wu drums, and many Jiyue masks introduced from the Tang dynasty recorded in the Xida temple's assets account; There are also individual records of Tang Chuan musical instruments in other places. For example, the old lacquer Qin in Nara FaLong temple is called leiqin or Kaiyuan Qin. In addition to the above 29 kinds of Tang Dynasty musical instruments, there are also five kinds of Tang Dynasty musical instruments: singing dysprosium, tin stick, bell, duo and chime. Because they are mainly used as Buddhist instruments, they are not included in the musical instruments here.

III. application of Japanese tangchuan musical instruments

1. tangchuan musical instruments in Japanese Yayue

The "music of the left" and "music of the right" formulated by Japan in the middle of the Ping'an Dynasty are equivalent to China's "two part trick". The music of the left is mainly Chinese music, including Indian music. The music on the right is mainly Korean music,

including the music of Bohai State. Therefore, the former is also called Tang music, and the latter is called gaolile. Japan respects the left, and the left giant is above the right minister. In almost all respects, the left is more respected than the right.

There are differences between the music of the left and the music of the right in terms of instrument types and instrument arrangements. The wind instruments on the left include dragon flute (horizontal flute), Chenli and Sheng. Although Chenli is used in the instruments on the right, in principle, Sheng is not used, and there is no dragon flute, but other forms of flute are used instead. In string instruments, there are zither and Pipa on the left. In principle, string instruments are not used on the right. In percussion music, the left uses drum, drum and drum, while the right uses three drums to replace the scorpion drum.

Therefore, on the whole, the Tang Dynasty Daqu is the center of Japanese Yayue, but the Japanese Yayue and the Tang Yanyue Daqu have their own styles in performance. Among them, the composition of musical instruments is a thought-provoking issue in the comparison of Japanese Tui music and Tangyan music Daqu. There are many kinds of musical instruments mobilized in the performance of Tangyan music. As many as 26 kinds of musical instruments are used only in zuobuji, while 8 kinds of musical instruments are used in the orchestras of Japanese Yayue (left side music, 3 pipes: Sheng, Naoli, HengDi; 2 strings: Pipa, Zheng; 3 drums: Taigu, Zhenggu, Jiegu), and 6 kinds of musical instruments are used in the accompaniment of dance music (except string instruments). In the composition of musical instruments of Tangyan music Daqu, about 10 kinds of foreign musical instruments are used only for sitting part, such as Jiegu and pipa, which play a larger role in the performance of Tangyan music. They both undertake the task of solo, sometimes also participate in ensemble, and have high requirements for performance techniques. In Japanese juvenile music, Pipa only exists as a rhythmic instrument. For example, the Sheng in Japanese Yayue music can play 15 notes (a b、c、d、e、f、g、#g、a、b、e、c、d、e、f), The Tang Sheng preserved in zhengcangyuan is 17 tubes, which can play 17 notes. Compared with the Sheng used in Japanese Tui music, it can play two notes F and a, and all the notes can play five or six harmonies. This situation shows that in the large-scale and systematic music form, China and Japan have different understanding of musical instruments, and Japanese music is still far from Chinese music in terms of the ability of scale combination. For the functional understanding of Pipa in timbre and participation in music organization, the Japanese music industry has always had a different understanding from Chinese music, which may be related to the national psychology caused by different geographical factors. Relying on the vast territory and cultural pattern, the music of the Tang Dynasty has a grand atmosphere, which can transform the desolate timbre into an interesting element. However, the Japanese music form is based on the island psychology, and its harmony and compatibility with the music of musical instruments are relatively limited.

2. Tangchuan musical instruments in Japanese localized music

Not only do Japanese Yayue have the use of tangchuan musical instruments, but also tangchuan musical instruments are widely used in Japanese localized music.

(1) Horse Music: it was produced in the early Heian era in Japan. Queen Hiroi, who died in the first year of Zhenguan (859), is a master of horse music. She also taught music techniques to many people in Jamaica. The ancient Japanese classics "pillow grass" and "tale of Genji" both recorded the relevant contents of horse music.

At that time, the accompanying instruments used for the horse urging music were as mentioned above. The left side music used wind instruments: Sheng, Chenli and dragon flute; Stringed instrument: Pipa, Zheng and the easy beat held by the singing protagonist (called sentence head or beat). Three other percussion instruments have been used: drum, Jiegu and Wugu. Later, as a percussion instrument, only Yi beat played with two boards in both hands (Yi) and the side of Yi with the right hand, knocking on the plane of Yi with the left hand to make a sound. Later, the official number of performers of Chuma music was Sheng, Ge CE and long Di, two Pipa and Zheng, one chief (sentence beginning) of the song and eight assistant singers (paying the song)

(2) Lang Yong is a popular singing form of Chinese poetry and prose accompanied by musical instruments in Japan's aristocratic society in the middle of the Heian era. Accompaniment instrument: Lang Yong pays more attention to vocal music standard than the horse urging music. Its accompaniment is different

from the horse urging music. It does not use string instruments, nor does it need to change the beat. It only uses Sheng, Chenli and dragon flute.

IV. integration of musical instruments by the Japanese court

Sorting out and integrating musical instruments is an important part of the reform of the Japanese court music system. Yoshikawa Yingshi pointed out that, taking string instruments as an example, the sinra (gayer) used in sinra music, the Baekje (Sheng Shi) used in Baekje music, the Qin (seven stringed Qin) used in Chinese music, as well as the zither, Ruan Xian, five stringed and so on, have all been discontinued. In wind instruments, the large shaped Sheng (called pole), big chestnut, Xiao, Chiba ("ancient Chiba" or "zhengcangyuan Chiba"), Mo mu, and so on, which can emit bass, have also been discontinued. At the same time, Korean music and Japanese traditional music have also been reformed. Chinese musical instrument performance has been added to it, and Naoli is a representative. Because the Naoli of Korea is different from that of China, Japan is called Tuge Naoli. The reason for the elimination of musical instruments is mainly due to the natural choice of music tones and scales, and may also be due to the inconvenience of operation, the complexity of playing technology and other negative reasons. In this regard, the view of Japanese scholar Yoshikawa Yingshi is: "in fact, the more important reason is that they were eliminated due to their discord with the feelings and interests of the Japanese, which has positive significance. For example, the abolition of bass instruments such as vertical and big Japanese Kuri reflects this meaning."

(Pipa music score preserved in Japan from the Tang Dynasty.)

"Youlan in Jieshi Diao", a copy of the pipa from the Empress Wu of the Tang Dynasty, which existed in Japan before the Tang Dynasty, is still a script, while Cao Roushi of the Tang Dynasty made a reduced script to replace the script.

The twenty characters of Pipa score preserved in Japan during the Tang Dynasty are basically the same

as those used in Dunhuang Pipa score during the Five Dynasties. According to, the characters of Pipa score preserved in Japan were obtained from users in the Tang Dynasty of China, so the characters of Pipa score must have appeared in the Tang Dynasty. And I believe that before it, just like the guqin, it was narrated in words.

The gongchi score, known as the Banzi score of Yan music in the Northern Song Dynasty, shows that it is very related to Yan music. Because the Yan music is a wind music tune, not a Pipa tune, it must be the beginning of the Yan music and the use of notation, just like the ancient Qin and pipa, to replace the previous written narration.

According to the description of words, we can see from the text of Xun Xu's three tunes on the flute in the early Western Jin dynasty recorded in the history of the Song Dynasty and the annals of the law, that from the Han and Wei dynasties to the Western Jin Dynasty, the wind instrument Zhidi was recorded by narration without the formation of a spectrum, that is, the gongchi spectrum did not appear in the Han, Wei and Jin Dynasties.

In the book of the Song Dynasty, the annals of the law recorded an event about Xun Xu's three tunes on the flute in the early Western Jin Dynasty. When Xun Xu asked the king of flute and the musician about the way he played the flute, he answered, "according to the legend of our ancestors, playing the flute, but using the words of composition, we should raise a finger for a song. At first, we didn't know what the sound of the seven holes should be." lie and the king of flute on that day said that the way to play the flute was to learn a finger from a song, and at first, we didn't know what the sound of the seven holes should be. ". If there was a meter score at that time, you should know "what sound should be" according to the instruction of a certain word of the meter, but there was no meter score on that day. The master taught you to pronounce a certain sound with "a finger", and taught it one by one until the whole song was finished. You should recite it one by one, but you don't know what sound it is ("what sound should be", that is, you don't know whether it's a working sound, a meter sound, an upper sound, or an ordinary sound, etc.), that is, you know that there is no meter score on that day.

Four years later, the Western Jin dynasty fell and entered the southern and Northern Dynasties. Yanle from the western regions of the North entered central China, so the so-called gongchi notation, formerly known as "yanle Banzi notation", came into being after yanle entered central China.

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